

TEACHING COMPETENCIES OF TEACHERS AND STUDENT ENGAGEMENT IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Teaching Competencies of Teachers and Student Engagement in Physical Education

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine which domain of teaching competencies of teachers best influenced engagement of Senior High School Physical Education students. A total of 150 students from Cluster 1 schools of Davao City division were identified through a simple random sampling. The study utilized a quantitative non-experimental method of research using correlational technique. Mean, Pearson *r*, and regression analysis were used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed a high level of physical teaching competencies of teachers. Similarly, students also demonstrated a high level of engagement in physical education. Moreover, the results showed a significant relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and engagement of Senior High School students in physical education. Further, teaching competencies significantly influence engagement of Senior High School students in physical education. However, no domain of teaching competencies of teachers best influences engagement of Senior High School students in physical education.

Keywords: *education, teaching competencies, student engagement, physical education*

Introduction

Educators have seen encouraging disengaged students to be active at school as one of their major challenges they face at school (Cothran & Ennis, 2000; Harris, 2008; Willms, 2013). Fox (2011) claims that boredom comes as a result of a lack of engagement. It causes children to become inattentive. High school students in the United States are not fully engaged in classroom learning (Cardwell, 2011). In addition, boredom weakens focus, desire, behavior mechanisms, and performance of students in the universities as revealed by many studies. Another issue of student engagement is their lack of participation. Studies indicate that students continue to remain passive members of the classroom environment and as a result do not capitalize on the benefits of participation (Susak, 2016). Students are not responding to the methods being implemented showing that an overall solution has yet to be found.

Also, educators have recognized the importance of engagement of students (Wang & Degol, 2014). This served as an integral component of learning and considered as a focus of a number of research studies. Also, it contributes to improve academic as measured by grade reports and standardized test scores (Cardwell, 2011). Additionally, when students are engaged with other students, it increases their active participation and achievement in the course material which also enhances their critical thinking skill and personal development (Pike, Kuh, & McCormick, 2011). Hence, assessing engagement is important because the extent and quality of their engagement predicts their academic development (Jang, Kim, & Reeve, 2012). Additionally, it yields variability due to instruments belong to different perspectives which provide variety of functions (Wang, Willet, & Eccles, 2011).

Locally, Senior High School students lack engagement in physical education activities due to concentration of the selected tracks chosen hence the number hours of engagement is only one hour a week. Eventually, they become less engaged that would make them physically fit. Solely, this manifestation has been evident in the learning environment that must be given prim importance by curriculum developers and education personnel. Nevertheless, limited literatures have indicated the link between teaching competencies and student engagement. Past studies on the engagement of students found that there is a correlation between students' engagement and the teaching competencies and academic achievement (Shaari, Yusoff, Ghazali, Osman, & Dzahir, 2014). Proposition of Schunk and Pajares (2005) claim that students who are competent and engaged able to establish objectives and supportive environments, use strategies, monitor and evaluate their work progress which makes them an effective learners. Additionally, students with high self-efficacy, accomplished their goals, face difficult activities, persistent and use adaptive approaches in responding to the difficulties which creates a positive effect in their engagement and achievement.

Ultimately, with the findings stated above, this study would like to determine the relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Few studies have been able to associate the two variables. Previous studies have only focused on the significance of each variable, yet no association has been established by researchers. Hence, it leaves a big gap for failing to establish link between the two variables specifically in physical education. Nevertheless, establishing the correlation between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education is significant since that we are still in the implementation phase of the Senior High School program, information about the results of the study would challenge curriculum planners to integrate and lengthen physical education in all tracks taken by students. More importantly, the success of this undertaking would produce excellent teachers and competitive students.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to determine which domain of teaching competencies of teachers best influences student engagement in Physical Education. Specifically, it sought to attain the objectives displayed below:

1. To ascertain the level of teaching competencies of teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 planning;
 - 1.2 development; and
 - 1.3 result.
2. To assess the level of student engagement in physical education in terms of:
 - 2.1 future goals and aspirations;
 - 2.2 control and relevance of school work;
 - 2.3 family support for learning;
 - 2.4 peer support for learning; and
 - 2.5 teacher- student relationships.
3. To determine the significant relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education.
4. To find out which domain of teaching competencies of teachers best influences student engagement in physical education.

Methodology

Highlighted in this section is the method of the study. This includes the research design, research locale, population and sample, research instrument, data collection, statistical tools, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The study utilized non- experimental quantitative research design using correlational technique. Non-experimental design involves variables that are not manipulated by the researcher and instead are studied as they exist (Belli, 2008). In this study, the variables utilized were not manipulated by the researcher, yet, the data for these variables were obtained through survey. Similarly, quantitative design refers to organize empirical analysis of observable phenomena through statistical tools. The purpose of this design was to develop and utilize mathematical models, theories and hypotheses pertaining to phenomena. The process of measurement is central to quantitative design because it provides the fundamental connection between empirical observation and mathematical expression of quantitative relationships (Given, 2008). In this study, this measures the level of the variables used in the study. The descriptive, correlational and regression analysis of the data were presented and discussed.

Meanwhile, correlation design was used to measure the degree of association of two or more variables (Creswell, 2012). Additionally, this design used numerical data to explore relationship among teaching method, learning style and academic performance of the students. Further, correlation study measures the strength and the direction of the relationship (Asaad, 2010). Likewise, correlational research comprises of collecting data to determine whether a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables (Brewer, 2000). In the context of the study, this design determines significant relationship between teaching competencies and student engagement in physical education.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 150 grade 12 senior high school students in the Cluster 1 schools of Davao City division. Cluster 1 is composed of schools with school codes 304366, 341409, 304360, 304391, and 300557.

From this context, the study used simple random sampling technique. Simple random sampling is a subset of sample chosen from a larger population. Each individual is chosen randomly and entirely by chance, such that each individual has the same probability of being chosen at any stage during the sampling process, and each subset of k individuals has the (Yates, Moore & Starnes, 2008).

Meanwhile, the inclusion criterion only considered students who were officially enrolled in the SHS program. Also, students with physical education subjects became respondents of the study. Only Grade 12 Senior High School students in cluster 1 schools were included in the study.

Further, under the exclusion criterion, Junior high school students were excluded in the study. Also, students who were not taking physical education were not considered as respondents. Senior High School students who were not enrolled in the cluster 1 schools were excluded from the study.

Instruments

This study adapted two questionnaires which cover teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Under teaching competencies of teachers' questionnaire, this consists of planning, development, and result. The questionnaire was taken from Moreno-Murcia et al., (2015). Planning comprises four items, development with 17 items, and result with seven items.

Indicated below is the numeric equivalent and descriptive interpretation used in determining teaching competencies of teachers.

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20-5.00	Very High	This indicates that teaching competencies of teachers are always manifested
3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that teaching competencies of teachers are often times manifested
2.60-3.39	Moderate	This indicates that teaching competencies of teachers are sometimes manifested
1.80-3.39	Low	This indicates that teaching competencies of teachers are rarely manifested
1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that teaching competencies of the teachers are never manifested

On the other hand, student engagement in physical education questionnaire comprises of future goals and aspirations, control and relevance of schoolwork, family support for learning, peer support for learning, and teacher-student relationships. This was taken from Appleton et al. (2006).

Indicated below is the numeric equivalent and descriptive interpretation used in determining student engagement in physical education questionnaire.

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20-5.00	Very High	This indicates that student engagement in physical education is always manifested in school
3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that student engagement in physical education is oftentimes manifested in school
2.60-3.39	Moderate	This indicates that student engagement in physical education is sometimes manifested in school
1.80-2.59	Low	This indicates that student engagement in physical education is rarely manifested in school
1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that student engagement in physical education is never manifested in school

The questionnaires were subjected to content validation by pool of experts prior to its distribution to the identified respondents. The results of the validation indicated a mean rating of 4. After it was validated, pilot testing was conducted. This was administered to students not covered in the study. The main purpose is to check consistency of students' responses based on the items indicated in the questionnaire. The result obtained a Cronbach alpha of 0.97.

Procedure

In the gathering of data, several steps were carried out. First, a written request was submitted to the Office of Division Superintendent requesting permission to conduct the study. After it was approved, individual letter was submitted to the principal of respective schools namely 304366, 341409, 304360, 304391, and 300557. Grade 12 Senior High School students of the said schools were identified as respondents of the study. Second, the researcher adapted two survey questionnaires that measure teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Third, questionnaires were subjected to validation by pool of experts to determine appropriateness of the items. Fourth, after validating the questionnaires, pilot testing was executed. This was administered to students not covered in the study. Fifth, after passing validation and reliability check, questionnaires were set for administration.

Sixth, during the administration of survey questionnaires, the researcher reported to the school principal for protocol purposes. The letter approved by the Superintendent was presented. Then, school principals were informed on the purpose and duration of the study. Seventh, the researcher directly administered the questionnaire to the identified respondents. Retrieval of questionnaires took time may be days or weeks. Eighth, after administration of survey questionnaires, responses of students were encoded in the appropriate data format. Ninth, this was imported to SPSS workspace for analysis. Tenth, results of the analysis were used for the final draft of the paper.

Statistical Tools

In the analysis of data, the following statistical tools were utilized: Mean was used to determine the level of teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Pearson r was used to determine the significant relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Regression was used in determining the influence of teaching competencies of teachers on student engagement in physical education.

Ethical Considerations

The content of this significant study was reviewed by the University of Mindanao Ethics Committee pertaining to the ethical principles set forth. First was informed consent. Prior to the conduct/administration of survey questionnaire, a permission letter was sent ahead of time to the public school heads concerned. Then, the letter was delivered to the identified respondents. Respondents were oriented on the processes/ mechanisms and purpose of the study. They were not forced to participate in the study if it is against on their will.

Second element was the anonymity and confidentiality of the data and the respondent. Effort is made to maintain anonymity in any written work resulting from this study. Pseudonyms were utilized to identify any printed materials and not to divulge determining marks of the respondents. The responses of the respondents were kept with confidentiality. Divulging information about the result is a violation of ethics of research.

Third was the freedom to withdraw. They were not forced to answer questions if they feel that it is against on their rights. They were

given freedom to stop or participate at any time. Fourth was intrusiveness. The time of the students were disturbed or intruded. Communication letter was sent in advance for the students to arrange their schedule and not to disturb their schedule. Fifth was physical risk. It was made sure that respondents were secured during the time they answer the questionnaire. They were not forced to answer when they feel it is not convenient.

Sixth was respect and honesty. Every response in the questionnaire was honored and respected. No fabrication was made. Result of the analysis of data was accepted and presented with all honesty. Respondents were informed about the results of the study.

Seventh, the success of this study benefitted several stakeholders. One is the teacher, this will enable the teacher to improve his/her competence. Also, it enables the teachers to explore more approaches and innovations that would aid him/her in classroom instruction. Moreover, this will provide assessment or evaluation on teachers' performance. Another beneficiary is the students, this will give students opportunity to be engaged to more challenging and holistic activities that will test their skills and abilities. In addition, this will measure their physical strength and fitness that will make them competitive students.

Eight the respondents of this study were the Senior High School students with Physical Education subject. Also, these respondents were coming from the Cluster 1 schools in the division of Davao City. Meanwhile, since the study was not experimental in nature, addressing the safe handling and containment of infectious microorganisms and hazardous biological materials were not included in this study. Ninth, there were no issues in terms of technology since the questionnaire was handed to the respondent. They were oriented on the processes/ mechanisms and purpose of the study. Communicating with the panel members and respondents through online was not observed in this study.

Moreover, other ethical issues were considered on the ground of establishing originality of the paper. The paper was subjected to plagiarism test using Turnitin. This was facilitated by the University of Mindanao personnel. In the case of fabrication, data gathered were made sure that these were stored in proper places. These were stored in portable external hard drive or personal computer or e-mail that only the researcher knows its location. Another issue was deceit, this was prevented by presenting the true results of the analysis as depicted in the statistical outputs. Also, respondents were well-informed of their participation in the study. Further, the results of the study were disseminated through public forum.

Further, results of the SPSS as output of the study were presented. This was done for the purpose of verifying the results of the analysis. Also, permission from the division Superintendent to conduct survey was first accomplished before conducting survey to the respective respondents. Lastly, in the case of authorship, the advisee-adviser needs to talk regarding this matter.

Results

This section highlights the results generated from the data analyzed. The discussion focused on the variables utilized in the study namely, teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. The descriptive aspect of the variables is discussed first, then, the significance of the relationship between the variables is presented next. The discussion ends with determining which teaching competencies domains predicts student engagement in physical education.

Teaching Competencies of Teachers

Presented in Table 1 is the level of teaching competencies of teachers. It tallies an overall mean rating of 3.93 which is described as high indicating that teaching competencies of teachers are oftentimes manifested. Teaching competencies of teachers comprise of planning, development, and result. Planning obtained a mean rating of 3.81, development with mean rating of 4.04, and result registers mean rating of 3.94. The three indicators mark high descriptive rating. The highest indicator is development which garners a mean rating of 4.04 which is interpreted as high. This indicates that teaching competencies of teachers are oftentimes manifested in terms of development. The standard deviation marks as 0.56 which indicates that there is homogeneity of responses among respondents. Majority of the items display high descriptive ratings.

Table 1. Level of Teaching Competence of Teachers

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Planning	0.73	3.81	High
Development	0.56	4.04	High
Result	0.68	3.94	High
Overall	0.58	3.93	High

Student Engagement in Physical Education

Displayed in Table 2 is the level of student engagement in physical education of senior high school students. It records an overall mean rating of 3.86 or high. This means that student engagement in physical education of senior high school students in Cluster 1 of Davao City Division is oftentimes manifested in school. The standard deviation tallies as 0.56 which suggests homogeneity of responses among senior high school respondents.

Indicators of student engagement in physical education comprise of future goals and aspirations with mean rating of 4.64, and control and relevance of school work with mean rating of 4.25. These indicators are interpreted with very high ratings. Similarly, other

indicators are family support for learning with mean rating of 4.11, peer support for learning with mean rating of 3.87, and teacher-student relationship with mean rating of 3.86. These three indicators are interpreted with high ratings.

Table 2. *Level of Student Engagement in Physical Education*

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Future Goals and Aspirations	0.47	4.64	Very High
Control and Relevance of School Work	0.51	4.25	Very High
Family Support for Learning	0.69	4.11	High
Peer Support for Learning	0.49	3.87	High
Teacher – Student Relationships	0.56	3.86	High
Overall	0.56	3.86	High

Significance on the Relationship between Teaching Competencies of Teachers and Student Engagement in Physical Education

Highlighted in Table 3 is the significance in the relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Results revealed an overall r- value of 0.260 with a p- value of 0.001 which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that as teaching competencies of teachers’ increases, student engagement in physical education also increases.

Further, individual correlation between indicators of teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education are also presented in the table. As shown in the table, the r- values and p- values for the relationships between indicators of teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education are presented as follows: planning tallies an r- value of 0.186 with 0.023 p- value; development marks an r- value of 0.232 with a p-value of 0.004; and result registers an r- value of 0.277 with a p-value of 0.001.

Table 3. *Significance in the relationship between Teaching Competencies of Teachers and Student Engagement in Physical Education*

Teaching Competencies	Student Engagement					Overall
	Future Goals and Aspirations	Control and Relevance of School Work	Family Support for Learning	Peer Support for Learning	Teacher – Student Relationships	
Planning	.109 (.183)	.178* (.029)	.030 (.719)	-.004 (.965)	.186* (.023)	.186* (.023)
Development	.267** (.001)	.431** (.000)	.166** (.043)	.077 (.349)	.232** (.004)	.232** (.004)
Result	.302** (.000)	.474** (.000)	.195** (.017)	.158 (.054)	.277** (.001)	.277** (.001)
Overall	.249** (.002)	.397** (.000)	.141 (.095)	.085 (.301)	.260** (.001)	.260** (.001)

Significance on the Influence of Teaching Competencies of Teachers on Student Engagement in Physical Education

Exemplified in Table 4 is the significance on the influence of parental teaching competencies of teachers on student engagement in physical education. It registers a p- value of 0.008 which is less than 0.05, thus, showing significant influence with an F- value of 4.076. Meanwhile, the result tallies with an R2 value of 0.077 which implies that 7.7 percent of the variance in student engagement in physical education is explained by the indicators of teaching competencies of teachers. The remaining percentage cannot be accounted to the indicators of teaching competencies of teachers. This shows that in their singular capacities, the indicators of teaching competencies cannot influence student engagement. However, their combined ratings show significant influence.

Based on the result, none of the domains of teaching competencies of teachers best influences student engagement in physical education as depicted by p-values which are greater than 0.05 in the level of significance.

Table 4. *Significance on the Influence of Teaching Competencies of Teachers on Student Engagement in Physical Education*

Teaching Competencies (Indicators)	Student Engagement			
	B	B	t	Sig.
Planning	0.018	0.024	0.220	0.826
Development	0.023	0.023	0.163	0.871
Result	0.200	0.244	1.853	0.066
R	0.278			
R ²	0.077			
F	4.076			
P	0.008			

Discussion

This section presented the discussion of the results of the variables analyzed in the study. First, the descriptive results of the variables are highlighted. In addition, correlation between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education is discussed and interpreted. Further, the discussion ends on determining the influence of teaching competencies of teachers on the student engagement in physical education.

Teaching Competencies of Teachers

The high level of teaching competencies of teachers is due to the high rating given by the students on teachers' planning, development, and result. The teachers have efficiently incorporate and employ ICTs (Information and Communication Technologies), and have a good command of the contents of the course. They facilitate student-student and student-professor interaction. Also, they inform the students of the competencies they will be expected to acquire. These manifestations or activities are expected to increase or enhance teaching competencies in the classroom since it is congruence to the ideas of White (2012), Partnership for 21st Century Skills (2010), Amanulla and Aruna (2014), and Muraina and Muraina (2015) who pronounced that teaching competencies would increase if proper planning, development, and positive result would be manifested by teachers, among others.

Student Engagement in Physical Education

The high level of student engagement in physical education is due to students' high response on family support for learning, peer support for learning, and teacher-student relationships. The students believed that their family wants them to keep trying when things are tough in school. Also, they believed that other students at school care about him/her. Additionally, they believed that his/her teachers are there for him/her when he/she need them. These manifestations are calculated to enhance students' engagement in physical education since these are in agreement with the views of Klauda (2009), Garn et al. (2011), and Gallagher (2018) that student engagement in physical education would increase if family-support, peer-support, and teacher-student relationships are taken into considerations and have given so much attention in school, among others.

Significance on the Relationship between Teaching Competencies of Teachers and Student Engagement in Physical Education

The correlation between variables reveals significant relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Planning, development, and result were the indicators of teaching competencies of teachers that significantly contributed to the overall positive significant relationship. This means that increasing teaching competencies of teachers leads to an increase on student engagement in physical education. Further, the result indicates that planning, development, and result contributed a big impact on student engagement in physical education.

Further, the results generated a positive correlation between variables in the study. Its proposition was directed on finding the relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education. Hence, the null hypothesis indicating no significant relationship between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement in physical education is therefore rejected.

Further, the data indicated that when teaching competencies of teachers is increased it resulted to an increase in student engagement in physical education. This claim is in consonance with the proposition of Schunk and Pajares (2005) who indicated that students who perceive themselves as effective in learning tend to be competent and engaged, to set goals, to use learning strategies, to monitor and evaluate their work progress, and to create support environments. Additionally, students with a high self-efficacy, compared to those with low self-efficacy, are more likely to outline success goals, to face challenging tasks, to be persistent and to adopt strategies to respond to challenges, with a positive impact in engagement and academic performance.

In addition, students' involvement in academic will influence the students' psychosocial development throughout his/her academic life as claimed by Astin (1984). To ensure the academic excellence, it requires actions and cooperation from all parties. The learning environment which is inviting, conducive and fun is essential in teaching and learning. This is because the students' ability and readiness to learn does not only depend on the students themselves, but also lie in the suitability of a teacher's style or competencies (Felder & Henriques, 1995). Further, teachers' competencies play a significant role on students' ability to respond in the instructions given to them. Solely, their ability to engage is dependent on teachers' mechanisms on managing the classroom. The more the teacher is prepared, the higher the chance of students' getting involved in class activities.

Significance on the Influence of Teaching Competencies of Teachers on Student Engagement in Physical Education

In this section, Linear Regression Analysis was utilized to test the significant influence of teaching competencies of teachers on student engagement in physical education. The predictors of teaching competencies of teachers were planning, development, and result. Based on the results, there is no domain of teaching competencies of teachers that best predicts student engagement in physical education in their singular capacities but when taken together, there is a significant relationship as shown with the overall p-value of less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted.

In addition, students' involvement in academic will influence the students' psychosocial development throughout his/her academic life

as claimed by Astin (1984). To ensure the academic excellence, it requires actions and cooperation from all parties. The learning environment which is inviting, conducive and fun is essential in teaching and learning. This is because the students' ability and readiness to learn does not only depend on the students themselves, but also lie in the suitability of a teacher's style or competencies (Felder & Henrique, 1995). Further, teachers' competencies play a significant role on students' ability to respond in the instructions given to them. Solely, their ability to engage is dependent on teachers' mechanisms on managing the classroom. The more the teacher is prepared, the higher the chance of students' getting involved in class activities.

Conclusion

The results revealed that the level of teaching competencies of teachers was labeled as high. The level of student engagement in physical education was described as high. There was significant relationship between teaching competencies of teachers on student engagement in physical education. Hence, an increased teaching competencies of teachers, increases student engagement in physical education. Moreover, no single domain of teaching competencies of teachers' best influenced student engagement in physical education; but when combined, there is significant influence. Furthermore, the results affirm the proposition of Felder and Henrique (1995) that students' engagement and readiness to learn does not only depend on the students themselves, but also lie in the suitability of a teacher's competencies. Hence, teachers' competencies play a significant role on students' engagement to respond in the instructions given to them

From conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are suggested. Planning may be well intensified by teachers before executing an action. Careful planning on the lessons to be discussed may be formulated first so that a clear picture on the delivery of instruction is captured. Teacher-student relationships may be observed for an efficient interaction and close monitoring of students performance. In doing so, this will establish an atmosphere of openness where students can freely express his/her ideas which in turn the teacher can give a valuable advice. The significant correlation between teaching competencies of teachers and student engagement suggests a need for teachers to set or create activities that would enhance engagement of students in physical education. School administration may perchance set a day for students to highlight engagement and socialization with their peers. Ultimately, other variables might be tested to test its influence on student engagement of Senior High School in physical education.

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